

Parent Application:ER/JH974/1

Project Title	UKRI transforming food systems- Study six: Farm tour pedagogies
Status	Approved
Email	J.Hsu@sussex.ac.uk
Phone No.	07897288203
Applicant Status	Staff (Research Fellow)
Department	SPRU - Science Policy Research Unit
Project Start Date	11-Jul-2022
Project End Date	31-Dec-2023
External Funding in place	Yes
External Collaborators	Yes
Funder/Project Title	
Name of Funder	Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council

Ethical Review Application ER/JH974/3 (continued)

Project Description

Funder/Project Title: Bbsrc-Biotechnology & Biological Sciences Research Council - Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities

Farm Tour Pedagogies is a research study that is part of the broader £6M UKRI-funded research programme 'Co-production of healthy, sustainable food systems for disadvantaged communities'.

This study is focused on understanding the broad educational experience of participants on farm tours for the Soil and the City project, which is funded by the Farming the Future organization. The Soil in the City project is coordinated by Brighton and Hove Food Partnership, Rock Farms, Feedback, and a network of Community Food Projects (CFP) in Brighton and Hove. Eight groups of CFP members will be brought to Rock Farm for a tour, in Horsham, over the period of about three months (July-September 2022). At the farm, participants are said to be able to choose from several activities, including farming and cooking experiences, therapy and leisure, and employability training.

The aim is to: 1) elucidate the participants' learning experience via the farm tours; and 2) understand how their learnings contribute to outcomes desired by their organisers. The first aim will be supported by observations and photographs of the farm tours. The second aim will be researched through semi-structured interviews with Soil in the City organisers (community food organisations that coordinate the farm visits).

This research study is part of the bigger UKRI-funded project. Dr Katerina Psarikidou and Dr Elaine Swan are the project research investigators based at the University of Sussex. Based on the principles of research co-production, the project is envisioned to provide citizens of socio-culturally diverse communities with choice and agency over the food they consume, the chains through which they access their food, and the policy frameworks that are needed to support the vision of a more inclusive and socio-environmentally just agri-food system for all.

Four community researchers will also be involved in doing observations and taking photos of the farm tours. These community researchers have been recruited by Brighton and Hove Food partnership to work on this and other research that is part of this larger project. The four researchers are long-time residents of Brighton and Hove and have are familiar with the community food hubs (CFH). They have been receiving research method training given by us. They will be trained in observation methods and photo taking in advance of the farm tours. They will abide by the details in this application as well as the British Sociological Association code: https://www.britisoc.co.uk/media/24310/bsa_statement_of_ethical_practice.pdf

But as their guidance on observations is limited and so they will also follow the Social Research Association code - see here <https://the-sra.org.uk/common/Uploaded%20files/ethical%20guide%20lines%202003.pdf>

Ethical Review Form Section A (ER/JH974/3)	
Question	Response
>> Checklist	
A1. Will your study involve participants who are currently or potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position (e.g. people under 18, people with learning difficulties, over-researched groups or people in care facilities)?	No
A2. Will participants be required to take part in the study without their consent or knowledge at the time (e.g. covert observation of people in non-public places), and / or will deception of any sort be used? Please refer to the British Psychological Society Code of Ethics and Conduct (or similar guidelines) for further information.	No
A3. Unless specifically and clearly consented (e.g. a media release form), will it be possible, through a research output, to identify participants in any way? (This does not include taking email details for participant prize draws or identifying participants from signed consent forms or holding identity encryption spreadsheets that are stored securely separate from the research data).	No
A4. Might the study induce psychological stress or anxiety, or produce humiliation or cause harm or negative consequences beyond the risks likely to be encountered in the everyday life of the participants?	Yes
A5. Is there a risk that the research topic might lead to disclosures from the participant concerning their beliefs, involvement in illegal actions or any other activities that may represent a threat to themselves or others?	No
A6. Will the study involve collecting any personal special category information* in a form that could allow the participant/ participants to be identified? [* identifiers relating to race, ethnic origin, politics, religion, trade union membership, philosophical beliefs, genetics, biometrics, health, sex life or sexual orientation]	Yes
A7. Will any drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) be administered as part of this study and will any invasive or potentially harmful procedures of any kind will be used?	No
A8. Will your project involve working with any substances and / or equipment which may be considered hazardous?	No
A9. Will your study involve the taking and/or storage of human tissue that falls under the Human Tissue Act (HTA)? http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/governance/erp_overview/humantissue	No
>> Risk Assessment	
A10. If you have answered Yes to ANY of the above questions, your application may be considered as HIGH risk. If, however you wish to make a case that your application should be considered as LOW risk please enter the reasons here. Researchers should note that SREOs or C-RECs may decide NOT to agree with the case that you have made.	

Ethical Review Form Section C (ER/JH974/3)	
Question	Response
>> Risk Checklist - Participants	
C1. Is DBS (Disclosure and Barring Service) clearance necessary for this project? If yes, please ensure you complete Section C24a below	No
C2. Are alcoholic drinks, drugs, placebos or other substances (such as food substances or vitamins) to be administered to the study participants?	No
C3. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to participants in this research?	
C4. Does the project involve working with any substances and/or equipment which may be considered hazardous? (Please refer to the University's Control of Hazardous Substances Policy http://www.sussex.ac.uk/hso/policies).	No
C5. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially have an emotionally disturbing impact on the researcher(s)?	Yes
C5a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to help the researcher(s) to manage this.	<p>There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices and understandings through the course of the research. The researchers are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing a participant led structure in methods, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time. Given the existing relationship with BHFP, all participants will be directed towards appropriate support services, should anything arise within interviews that may be distressing for participants. This includes but is not limited to: Access to emergency food provision; support with eating disorders and support with mental illness. The researchers and local gatekeepers are aware of organisations which could provide further help should signposting be required. In terms of the observations, we will ensure we respect privacy and are not invasive in our observations. All our observations will occur in the context of farm tour activities, with researchers also participating in the farm tour activities we will observe and have informal conversations related to the activity while doing the activity. Please see indicative questions related to these informal conversations for reference.</p> <p>We will explain this in our consent forms as well as at the beginning of each farm tour, and that people can request to be excluded from our photos and notes.</p>
C6. Could the nature or subject of the research potentially expose the researcher(s) to threats of physical violence and / or verbal abuse?	No
C6a. If yes, briefly describe what measures will be taken to mitigate this.	

C7. Does the research involve any fieldwork - Overseas or in the UK?	Yes
C7a. If yes, where will the fieldwork take place? (All research requiring overseas travel will require the submission of a fully completed OTTSRA form). In the event that the Foreign and Commonwealth Office has travel warnings in place for the country (ies) to be visited you will also need to provide a detailed risk assessment.	<p>Interviews with Rock Farm, the organization, and participants will take place at Rock Farm. Interviews with other Soil in the City partners will take place either online or at partner offices.</p> <p>Interviews done online will be on zoom for education supported by the University of Sussex platform. Researchers already have access to platform and are acquainted with security settings due to teaching commitments. Interviewees will be informed about that through the participant information sheets and asked to provide their consent to this.</p> <p>Participant observation (writing observation notes, taking photos, having informal conversations) will take place on hired minibuses for the tour, and at Rock Farm in Horsham.</p>
C8. Will any researchers be in a lone working situation?	No
C8a. If yes, briefly describe the location, time of day and duration of lone working. What precautionary measures will be taken to ensure safety of the researcher(s)?	
C9. Can you think of anything else that might be potentially harmful to the researcher(s) in this research?	No
>> Data Collection and Analysis (Please provide full details)	

C10. PARTICIPANTS: How many people do you envisage will participate, who are they, and how will they be selected?

1. 13 people - Semi structured interviews with Soil in the City project partners. These include the organisations Brighton and Hove Food Partnership, Rock Farm, Feedback, and 8 community food projects (CFP) in Brighton and Hove.

The CFP are either social supermarkets (hubs to purchase high-quality produce at a set members price), community organisations providing social supermarkets, or healthy lunch groups. They are located in the Hollingdean, Mile Oak, Whitehawk, Hove, Moulscomb neighborhoods, and Kemptown neighborhoods. Their names are:

- Phoenix Food Hub
- BrightStore
- Very Local Food Hubs
- Moulscombe Community Market
- Youth Advice Centre
- Pankhurst Pantry
- Lunch Positive
- Voices in Exile

Brightstore are running two separate tours.

2. 45 people (5 people for nine tours) Observations, photos, and informal conversations. Each group is made up of one of the above CFPs users.

For method 1, participants are selected because their organisations are organisers for the farm tours.

For method 2, participants are selected because they are members of one of the CFPs.

C11. RECRUITMENT: How will participants be approached and recruited?

For method 1 (written in question C10), participants (which are Soil in the City project partners) will be given participant information sheets through email. The lead partner organisation, Brighton and Hove Food Partnership, will identify participants within their organisation and partner organisations.

For method 2 (written in question C10), participants will be recruited via people who register for the Soil in the City farm visits through the Eventbrite website. They will be able to read the text from the participant information form through a University of Sussex Qualtrics survey link on the Eventbrite website, set up for the sole purpose in which participants enter their name and choose to provide their consent. They can read the participant information form directly on the Qualtrics survey, and choose on the survey to provide consent or not to join the research.

Community Food Hubs, which are social supermarkets (community hubs for shopping for high quality food items through a set membership price), in Brighton and Hove, announce the farm tours through their outreach channels. These include giving pamphlets about the event, one-on-one chats to people who visit their community food project, monthly newsletters that include event information, email list and social media announcements to members of their specific community food project.

At the start of each farm tour, we will meet with each participant for the first time, and will brief on the ethical process. The participants will have the opportunity to raise any questions about the project. The researchers will explain informed consent and go through the information sheet (that was in the Qualtrics survey) with individuals in person.

On the farm tour days, people be given verbal briefings. We will offer a verbal consent process to those who prefer that.

C12. METHOD: What research method(s) do you plan to use; e.g. interview, questionnaire/self-completion questionnaire, field observation, audio/audio-visual recording etc.?

1. Semi structured interviews with Soil in the City partners- see suggested questions. These will focus on the aspirations for the farm visit; and how they view them as contributing to social change with respect to the food system. Interviews with Rock Farm, the organization, will take place at Rock Farm. Interviews with other Soil in the City partners will take place either online or at partner offices. Some of these interviews will take also place on zoom for education supported by the University of Sussex platform. Researchers already have access to platform and are acquainted with security settings due to teaching commitments. Interviewees will be informed about that through the participant information sheets and asked to provide their consent to this. Zoom interviews will also be recorded on zoom. All interviews will be audio-recorded.

2. Observations, photos and informal conversations. The goal of this method is to use design ethnography (Pink 2008), which is a research method approach to explore how a spaces design interacts with a person using that space. This approach also considers people's lived experiences as vital to the experience with a given space. In the our case, we will learn about how the farm's spatial design enables participant learning; as well as how participant's daily food lives inform their encounter with the farm space and its activities. For instance, some of the participants eat the vegetables grown at Rock Farm and this method explores how encountering the growing processes of their eaten foods affects their perception of their food. Also, this method would explore how the farm tour informs their community food project experience.

Researchers, themselves, will be participants of the tourwe will join farm visit activities as hearing farm staff explain about on-site agriculture, observing the vegetables plots, and joining in planting crops. Simultaneously, researchers will take notes on the overall participant experience and educational of the farm visit, especially related to their own daily food lives. Researchers will also have informal conversations with the participants that connect to the activity that they are doing together. (Please see list of indicative questions for reference). These conversations will occur naturally while joining the activities. The conversations will not be audio recorded.

Researchers will take photos of key interactions of the participant with the farm space. These will include participants listening to the farm manager explaining about the farm or a section of the farm; picking vegetables; weeding vegetables; touching vegetables; using farm tools to prepare soil; eating together; socialising with each other and with farm staff; and any process related to learning about the farm (i.e. reading signage, inspecting vegetables for their maturity before harvest, and etc). We are also focused onhow the farm space's design and how it affords specific activitie as socialising, eating, harvesting, farm touring, and etc. We will take photos of specific design elements of the

farm that are important to interaction; as well as showing the interaction with that specific section of the farm.

We will ensure that faces and children will not be included in any photos. We are aware that observations/photos can be obtrusive, and will take extra care not interrupt conversations or activities, while keeping at a reasonable distance. Photos will only be taken only of those who provided written consent. Before the tour begins we will remind participants that they may withdraw consent of being photographed for any activity during the tour.

We will not coerce any conversations but will chat to participants with conversational questions natural to the tour or tour activity. Our partner, BHFP, are experts in running food programming and will provide guidance of mental health or food poverty resources if these issues arise in conversation.

<p>C13. LOCATION: Where will the project be carried out e.g. public place, in researcher's office, in private office at organisation?</p>	<p>Observations, photos, informal conversations will be carried out at Rock Farm in Horsham, the minibuses to and from the farm. Tour participants will be covered by our primary partner, Brighton and Hove Food Partnerships full public liability insurance.</p> <p>Interviews will take place either at Soil in the City partner offices or on zoom for education supported by the University of Sussex platform. Researchers already have access to platform and are acquainted with security settings due to teaching commitments. Interviewees will be informed about that through the participant information sheets and asked to provide their consent to this.</p>
<p>>> Ethical Considerations (Please provide full details)</p>	

C14. PARTICIPANT WELLBEING: Will the study involve engaging participants in the discussion of distressing or sensitive topics? (e.g. sexual activity, drug use, ethnicity, political behaviour, potentially illegal activities). If so, please set out how you will manage the well-being of participants.

There is potential for participants to experience some anxiety or stress about their food practices and understandings through the course of the research. The researchers are aware of the importance of maintaining boundaries with participants, for the wellbeing of both parties. By employing a participant led structure in the methods, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time.

Given the existing relationship with BHFP, all participants will be directed towards appropriate support services, should anything arise within interviews, mapping and other methods that may be distressing for participants. This includes but is not limited to:

Access to emergency food provision; support with eating disorders and support with mental illness. The researchers and local gatekeepers are aware of organisations which could provide further help should signposting be required.

Examples are as follows.

For Brighton and Hove, mental health:

Sussex Mental Healthline provides 24/7 psychological support for anyone with mental health concerns from registered clinicians.

Contact: freephone 0300 5000 101

Community Roots a network of local services committed to supporting good mental health and wellbeing in Brighton & Hove.

Contact: freephone 0808 196 1768 or online link

(https://www.uok.org.uk/talk-to-us?_ga=2.134930417.1879836360.1655196127-903895191.1655196127)

Food relief organisations in Brighton: the link below provides access to a range of food relief and poverty resources that could be given to participants depending on their needs.

<https://bhfood.org.uk/directory-hub/accessing-emergency-food-parcels/>

Participants will be able to withdraw at any point of any of the research activities, without having to provide any explanation.

They may request withdrawal of their data by 31 November 2022 which is four weeks after the research activity they have participated in and the start of our data analysis.

<p>C15. INFORMED CONSENT: Please describe the process you will use to ensure your participants are freely giving fully informed consent to participate. This will usually include the provision of an Information Sheet and will normally require a Consent Form unless there is justification for not doing so. (Please state this clearly).</p>	<p>For all the methods, participants will be encouraged to give their informed consent through two different types of consents: provision of information sheets and written consent forms; or and oral consent agreements.</p> <p>Also, we will also ensure that the researchers brief the consent process clearly at the beginning of the farm visit before our methods are undertaken.</p> <p>Lastly, we will ensure that participants can ask questions and understand what will happen to their data.</p>
<p>C16. RIGHT OF WITHDRAWAL: Participants should be able to withdraw from the research at any time. Participants should also be able to withdraw their data if it is linked to them and should be told when this will no longer be possible (e.g. once it has been included in the final report). Please describe the exact arrangements for withdrawal from participation and withdrawal of data for your study.</p>	<p>Participants will be able to withdraw at any point within the research activity or afterwards themselves, without having to provide any explanation. They may request withdrawal of their data by 31 November 2022 which is when the data collection is intended to finish.</p>
<p>C17. OTHER ETHICAL ISSUES: If you answered YES to anything in A.1 above (participants who are potentially vulnerable or unable to give informed consent or in a dependent position) you must specifically address this here. Please also consider whether there are other ethical issues you should be covering here. Please also refer to the professional code of conduct you intend to follow in your research.</p>	<p>The farm visits will involve photographing, observations, and informal conversations. This will be indicated in the consent forms, and we will not include faces in the photos. This will be explained on the consent form and before the start of the bus tours and make it clear that people can ask not to be photographed. We will avoid as much as possible photographing children. We will only use the photos for our analytic purposes.</p> <p>As sociologists, we generally follow the BSA code https://www.britsoc.co.uk/media/24310/bsa_statement_of_ethical_practice.pdf</p> <p>But their guidance on observations is limited and so we will follow the SRA code - see here https://the-sra.org.uk/common/Uploaded%20files/ethical%20guidelines%202003.pdf</p>
<p>>> Data Protection, Confidentiality, and Records Management</p>	
<p>C18. DPA: Will you ensure that the processing of personal information related to the study will be in full compliance with the Data Protection Act 2018 (GDPR)? Please give full details under C19a. (http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa)</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>C18a. C18a. If you are transferring any personal data outside of the United Kingdom, you must explain how you will comply with data protection legislation. Further guidance is available at: https://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/dpa/transfersoutside</p>	

C19. CONFIDENTIALITY: Will you take steps to ensure the confidentiality of personal information? Please explain how any identifiable personal records and research data will be managed and stored whilst ensuring that participants have given appropriate informed consent for this in C19a and or C20 below.	Yes
C19a. DATA MANAGEMENT: Please provide details of any anonymisation procedures and of physical and technical security measures (including secure storage) of identifiable personal and research data here. Indicate how these will be employed in the collection, analysis and research output and dissemination stages.	The names of all participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities although the limitations of this will be discussed with them given that photographs and recordings could lead to identifications. All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using OneDrive. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to OneDrive, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. The shared project workspace on OneDrive will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to the research team. Personal data in the form of photographs and recordings will be deleted at the end of the project.
C20. CONSENT: If personal information related to this study will be retained and shared (i.e. in outputs) in a form that is not fully anonymised (separated from information that can identify the participant) please outline how participants will be made aware of this (including any limitations) and indicate their consent.	
C21. Will the Principal Investigator take full responsibility during the study, for ensuring appropriate storage and security of information (including research data, consent forms and administrative records) and, where appropriate, will the necessary arrangements be made in order to process copyright material lawfully?	Yes
C21a. If you answered "No" to the above question, please give further details of how data and records will be managed:	
C22. Who will have access to personal information and data relating to this study?	The research team at Sussex which includes academics and a project manager.
C23. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN: AFTER the study: State how long study information including research data, consent forms and personal identification will be retained, in what format(s) and where the information will be kept. http://www.sussex.ac.uk/ogs/policies/information/recordsmanagementguidance	Anonymised data will be deposited in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) Figshare, where it will be preserved for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016) and to allow for maximum project exposure and impact. Any data that has identifiers, such as photos, will not be kept in the USRDR. Participants will be notified in the participant information that their data will be securely stored in accordance with GDPR requirements and will only be presented anonymously
>> Other Ethical Clearances and Permissions	

C24. Are any other ethical clearances or permissions (internal or external) required? Please see the help text (i) for further details.	No
C24a. If yes, please give further details including the name and address of the organisation. If other ethical approval has already been received please attach evidence of approval, otherwise you will need to supply it when ready. (You do not need to provide evidence of a current DBS check at this point).	

Dear Dr. Ruth Stirton,

Thank you for your helpful guidance on this ethics application. Below is a table indicating how the updated application responds to each of your points.

Many thanks again for your consideration.

Regards,

Jesse

<p>1 - In relation to Section C12 - please can you provide more detail regarding what will be photographed and observed and how you will navigate ethical issues in using these two methods.</p>	<p>C12 has been amended with these details. The revised text is as follows:</p> <p>'In the our case, we will learn about how the farm's spatial design enables participant learning; as well as how participant's daily food lives inform their encounter with the farm space and its activities. For instance, some of the participants eat the vegetables grown at Rock Farm and this method explores how encountering the growing processes of their eaten foods affects their perception of their food. Also, this method would explore how the farm tour informs their community food project experience. Researchers, themselves, will be participants of the tour we will join farm visit activities as hearing farm staff explain about on-site agriculture, observing the vegetables plots, and joining in planting crops. Simultaneously, researchers will take notes on the overall participant experience and educational of the farm visit, especially related to their own daily food lives. Researchers will also have informal conversations with the participants that connect to the activity that they are doing together. (Please see list of indicative questions for reference). These conversations will occur naturally while joining the activities. The conversations will not be audio recorded. Researchers will take photos of key interactions of the participant with the farm space. These will include participants listening to the farm manager explaining about the farm or a section of the farm; picking vegetables; weeding vegetables; touching vegetables; using farm tools to prepare soil; eating together; socialising with each other and with farm staff; and any process related to learning about the farm (i.e. reading signage, inspecting vegetables for their maturity before harvest, and etc). We are also focused on how the farm space's design and how it affords specific activities as socialising, eating, harvesting, farm touring, and etc. We will take photos of specific design elements of the farm that are important to interaction; as well as showing the interaction with that specific section of the farm. We will ensure that faces and children will not be included in any photos. We are aware that observations/photos can be obtrusive, and will take extra care not interrupt conversations or activities, while keeping at a reasonable distance. Photos will only be taken only of those who provided written consent. Before the tour begins we will remind participants that they may withdraw consent of being photographed for any activity during the tour. We will not coerce any conversations but will chat to participants with conversational questions natural to the tour or tour activity. Our partner, BHFP,</p>
--	--

	are experts in running food programming and will provide guidance of mental health or food poverty resources if these issues arise in conversation.'
2 - Please can you amend the withdrawal dates in Sections C16 and Section C14 so that they are the same.	Both sections now indicate the same date of '31 November 2022'
3 - In relation to Section C19a - ideally only anonymised transcripts will be kept on one drive and personal data can be deleted at the end of the project.	<p>This section has been amended to reflect that personal data will be deleted at the project's end. After repeated email correspondence with Tim Parkinson, Senior Research Ethics and Integrity Officer, he has assured me that photographs should be kept on One Drive as it is the most secure place to store them. The revised text reads as follows:</p> <p>'The names of all participants in the study will be anonymised in order to protect their identities although the limitations of this will be discussed with them given that photographs and recordings could lead to identifications. All data will be managed by the researcher and securely stored and transferred using OneDrive. Project passwords will be pre-set and will contain a combination of at least eight alphanumeric and symbolic characters. Once uploaded to OneDrive, original copies of data will be securely deleted from local storage locations. The shared project workspace on OneDrive will be maintained, organised and updated by the researcher, who will do weekly checks on version control, archiving, monitoring and tidying. All raw data files will be named with anonymous unique IDs and a password-protected database will keep record of links between unique IDs and personal data. Shared folders containing raw data will have access limited to the research team. Personal data in the form of photographs and recordings will be deleted at the end of the project.'</p>
4 - In relation to Section C23 - Please clarify that only anonymised data will be held in the data repository so nothing that identifies anyone such as photos etc would be deposited?	<p>C23 has been amended to reflect that photos will wnot be deposited. See the amended text:</p> <p>'Anonymised data will be deposited in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) Figshare, where it will be preserved for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016) and to allow for maximum project exposure and impact. Any data that has identifiers, such as photos, will not be kept in the USRDR. Participants will be notified in the participant information that their data will be securely stored in accordance with GDPR requirements and will only be presented anonymously.'</p>
5 - In relation to the Consent Form - Please add the date that participants need to have requested the withdrawal of their data by Please also add more information relating to the data repository, and how that may be used by others.	<p>These texts have been added to the Consent Form (please see new version in supportind documents:</p> <p>'Anonymised data will be kept in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) called Figshare. It will be there for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016). Only researchers on this project can access this data for the purpose of writing reports, publications, and presentations. Any data that has identifiers, such as</p>

	<p>photos, will not be kept in the USRDR. Photographic data will be destroyed at the completion of the project.'</p> <p>If you wish to withdraw from this research, please contact Dr. Jesse Hsu, the Research Fellow who is coordinating this project at J.Hsu@sussex.ac.uk by 31 November 2022.</p>
<p>6 - In relation to the Participant Information Sheet - please remove the word 'pedagogy' and instead perhaps use 'learning from farm tours'. You should also state how long data will be kept for on this document. Please also check this form for typos and explain exactly what kind of photos will be taken of participants.</p>	<p>Participant Information Sheet has been amended to include this information. Please refer to the new version of the sheet in the supporting documents.</p> <p>All typos have been eliminated.</p> <p>These written sections have been added:</p> <p>'Photos will be taken of you joining in activities, such as learning about agriculture, weeding, harvesting, walking around, socialising, and eating. The photos will show part of you including your clothing, but we will ensure that the photos do not contain faces, nor will not they contain children. If there is any activity you do not wish to be photographed, please let the researcher know and we will not include you in the photo.'</p> <p>Anonymised data will be kept in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) called Figshare. It will be there for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016).'</p> <p>Photographic data will be destroyed at the completion of the project.</p>
<p>7 - Please can you add the following sentence to the Participant Information Sheet 'if you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk)'.</p>	<p>Participant Information Sheet has been amended to include this information. Please see the new version of the sheet in the supporting documents.</p>
<p>8 - Please also add the UoS insurance statement onto the Participant Information Sheet as detailed in the template.</p>	<p>Participant Information Sheet has been amended to include this information. Please see the new version of the sheet in the supporting documents.</p>

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Study title: Learning from Farm Tours

INVITATION

You are invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether to take part, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully.

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE STUDY?

The purpose of this study is to understand more about people's learning experiences on the visit to Rock Farm and their relationship to food practices in the home and neighbourhood.

WHY HAVE I BEEN INVITED TO PARTICIPATE?

You have been invited to participate because you are an adult resident of the city of Brighton and Hove. We are interested in people's understandings of food and we think you have ideas and experiences which are important for researchers and policy makers to understand.

DO I HAVE TO TAKE PART?

No! It is up to you to decide whether to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign a consent form. You are however still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO ME IF I TAKE PART?

If you are a participant on the farm tour, you will take in *Informal Chats, observations, and photos*. Researchers will have informal conversations with you as you join the farm visit together. They will write observation notes and take photos about your experience during the various activities of the farm tour. Photos will be taken of you joining in activities, such as learning about agriculture, weeding, harvesting, walking around, socialising, and eating. The photos will show part of you including your clothing, but we will ensure that the photos do not contain faces, nor will they contain children. If there is any activity you do not wish to be photographed, please let the researcher know and we will not include you in the photo.

Farm visit participants will receive a small recompense in the form of a shopping voucher for their time.

If you are a Soil in the City project partner staff member, you will be taking part in an interview from 15-45 minutes to share your thoughts about the Soil in the City's project aims and its role in food systems change.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE DISADVANTAGES AND RISKS OF TAKING PART?

The primary disadvantage of participating in this study is the time taken to participate. Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress from discussing food will be kept to the minimum through the activities chosen, and the experience of the researchers. By employing exploratory research methods and an open structure to the discussions, the researcher will encourage participants to raise themes that are of importance in their own lives, making it clear that activities can stop or be redirected at any time.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

By taking part in this study, you are helping to expand knowledge on food practices in your neighbourhood and council area which can potentially influence future food-related policies. This data will be of potential benefit in informing the agendas of organisations concerned with food distribution within the area.

WILL MY INFORMATION IN THIS STUDY BE KEPT CONFIDENTIAL?

All information collected about you will be kept strictly confidential. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity will be ensured through strict adherence to the guidelines for storing, managing and processing data set out in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the UK Data Protection Act 2018. After the undertaking the research methods, only the researchers will have access to your data. We will keep all personal information about you (e.g. your name and other information about you that can identify you) confidential, that is we will not share it with others. We will also anonymise the written transcript produced by the transcriber. This means that we will remove any personal information.

All audio-visual data collected will be downloaded and stored securely on a University of Sussex managed storing system, named OneDrive.

Anonymised data will be kept in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) called Figshare. It will be there for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016). Only researchers on this project can access this data for the purpose of writing reports, publications, and presentations. Any data that has identifiers, such as photos, will not be kept in the USRDR. Photographic data will be destroyed at the completion of the project.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WANT TO TAKE PART?

To opt in for the study, please agree to take part by signing the consent form or agreeing to the oral consent.

WHAT SHOULD I DO IF I WISH TO WITHDRAW FROM THE STUDY AFTER JOINING?

You can withdraw if you wish. To do this, please contact Dr. Jesse Hsu, the Research Fellow who is coordinating this project at J.Hsu@sussex.ac.uk by 31 November 2022.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY?

The results of this research study will be used to inform several academic pieces of work. These may include: articles in published academic journals, academic book chapters, public presentations, conferences and/or events. Copies of any research output will be made freely available to all participants, although participants should note that this process is planned to take place over a 4-year period, with data retained for the length of that period. When writing up the findings from this study, we would like to reproduce some of the views and ideas you shared with us. We will only use anonymised quotes so that although we will use your exact words, we will do our best to ensure you cannot be identified in the publications, although we cannot guarantee this.

WHO IS ORGANISING AND FUNDING THE RESEARCH?

Research will be undertaken by members of the Management Department and Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU) at the University of Sussex. The project is part of a part of a study funded by the government agency, UK Research and Innovation "UKRI", entitled 'Transforming Food Systems for Disadvantaged Communities', which is administered at the University of Reading.

INSURANCE

The University of Sussex has insurance in place to cover its legal liabilities in respect of this study.

THANK YOU

if you have any questions or concerns relating to this research please contact Ruth Stirton, Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts Cross Schools Research Ethics Committee (r.stirton@sussex.ac.uk).

CONSENT FORM FOR PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

Title of Project: Food Lives: Farm Tour Pedagogies

Name of Researcher and School: Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management

Please tick
 YES NO

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I consent to participate in the following activities with the researchers – tick as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interview • Photos and observation notes • Informal conversations about the farm visit | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I consent to being informed about follow-up research activities and potential participation in future research. | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have read the information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and I understand the principles, procedures and possible risks involved. | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that personal data will be used for the purposes of this research study. I understand that such information will be treated strictly confidential and handled in accordance with Data Protection legislation. | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that any information given by me may be used in future reports, academic articles, publications or presentations by the researcher and the project team, but my personal information will not be included and I will not be identifiable. | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that data will be kept according to the university guidelines for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the study. | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I understand that my participation is voluntary, that I can choose not to participate in part or all of the project, and that I can withdraw at any stage of the project without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way. | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I agree to take part in the above University of Sussex research project | <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> |

Anonymised data will be kept in the University of Sussex Research Data Repository (USRDR) called Figshare. It will be there for at least 10 years post-project in line with the Concordat on Open Research Data (2016). Only researchers on this project can access this data for the purpose of writing reports, publications, and presentations. Any data that has identifiers, such as photos, will not be kept in the USRDR. Photographic data will be destroyed at the completion of the project.

If you wish to withdraw from this research, please contact Dr. Jesse Hsu, the Research Fellow who is coordinating this project at J.Hsu@sussex.ac.uk by 31 November 2022.

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Indicative questions for Soil in the City project staff members:

- What is the Soil in the City trying to accomplish?
- What is your vision of an ideal food system?
- If the food system changed for the best in the next decade, what would that look like?
- What are the processes of change that would need to happen for that food system to be realised?
- policies that can help towards that, or any working against that?
- What types of policies do you think are lacking locally, regionally, or nationally?
- Are there any policies that have particularly supported its development, or any policies that need to be developed to support that?
- How does this this program fit in your overall vision of a future food system?
- Why did you think this particular project design ('farm tours') would help contribute to your organisational aims?

Indicative questions for informal discussions with farm tour participants:

- Is this your first time to this farm?
- Have you been to a farm tour before?
- Why did you decide to join this farm visit?
- What do you think about the visit so far?
- Are there any activities that you are enjoying the most?
- Which part of the farm is most interesting to you?
- Is there anything surprising that you found on this farm tour?
- Do you garden?
- Do you find any of these vegetables at your community food project?
- Do use any of these vegetables at home?
- Which vegetable found on this farm is your favourite?

CHECKLIST: VERBAL CONSENT FROM RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS **FOR RESEARCHER USE ONLY**

Title of Project: **Farm Tour Pedagogies**

Name of Researcher and School: **Dr Elaine Swan, Dr Jesse Hsu, School of Management and Dr Katerina Psarikidou, SPRU**

C-REC Ref no: <Insert ER no.>

A. Process of obtaining verbal consent from research participants:

1) Give an account of how you will verbally **explain** to the research participants as clearly as possible

and in terms that they are familiar with:

- The **aims** and **objectives** of your research;
- The reasons why you have **selected** them for this research;
- The reasons why their story/knowledge/understanding/opinions are **relevant** to your research;
- The ways in which the research data will be **used**: for example, in a dissertation / thesis/publications/blogs/reports/policy documents.

Our research study, “Farm Visit Pedagogies” explores your overall experience and learnings on your trip to Rock Farm. We are part of a larger multi-university government-funded project on improving access to healthy food in the UK. You have been selected as a participant because you are a resident of one of the communities that we are researching.

Your expertise and experience with cooking and food provisioning in your community is important to us because your knowledge can inform future food policies. The research data collected for this project may be used for: for research reports, journal publications, book chapters, conference and workshop presentations, policy documents, blog posts, and food product development

Please expand the box as necessary

2) I will **verbally explain** to the research participants:

- That they can **withdraw** from the research at any time without giving a reason, and without being penalised or disadvantaged in any way and/or that they can tell me not to use certain types of information at any time;
- What **confidentiality** means in the context of the research and how confidentiality will be maintained in this particular context (OR explain why confidentiality cannot be maintained in this particular case – e.g. focus group);
- What **anonymity** means and how it will be maintained in this particular context (OR I will ask approval for the use of their name/location/company/organisation in the final report/dissertation/further publication).

Template approved by URGC May 2018

Farm Visit Pedagogies and Version 1. for Consent Form

3) Describe below how you will **verbally explain** to your informants that they can **withdraw** from the research at any time, what **confidentiality** and **anonymity** mean in your research context, and how you will explain these terms to your informants:

You may choose to withdraw from our research study at any point without having to provide us a reason. There will be no penalty to do so. You may also ask us to not use any data — recorded conversation,

photographs, observation notes— for the study or future research outputs such as journal articles, book chapters, conference presentations, policy reports, until November 1st 2022 when we begin our analysis. We will try to protect your anonymity but we cannot guarantee it because the photographs may contain images of objects which could potentially identify you. We will ensure written texts will not contain any identifiable features such as names, occupations, and detailed personal information unless you consent to these. Your names will be anonymised in our research databases order to protect your identity. All data collected for this project will be stored on a secure application called OneDrive which is licensed for the University of Sussex. We will have project passwords and store data on secure university storage systems. Once uploaded to OneDrive, all original data files will be deleted from researcher storage devices. All data files will be named using anonymous IDs.

1. 4) I will verbally **check** with the research participants that (tick, as applicable):

- They are happy to be interviewed and/or observed by me;
- They are happy for me to be present at and/or participate in their activities;
- They are happy for me to take notes on the interview/observations/interactions;
- They are happy for the interview/observation/interaction to be: photographed

- **Where photographs, video, or audio tape are to be shown to others, specific and separate consent should be sought in written, video or audio form.**
- **This consent should involve a full explanation of the kinds of contexts in which these media are to be shown.**

- **Media should not be published – online or elsewhere – without specific consent.**

They are happy to be contacted again for a further interview should that be required.

2. 5) I will give the research participants the opportunity to **ask any questions** about any of the above or any other concerns they may have.
3. 6) I understand that seeking verbal consent will involve explaining all I have documented above and that verbal consent is an ongoing process. I understand that I will need to document the ongoing process of verbal consent.

B. Process in which verbal consent cannot be obtained:

If participant observation and/or other ethnographic research methods will be used in which verbal consent will not or cannot be sought/obtained, the following need to be considered by the researcher:

- 1) Explain why the **aims and objectives** of the research cannot always be fully explained to the research participants (this might differ per group/individual):

Research aims and objectives can be fully explained to research participants

- 2) Explain why **confidentiality** and/or **anonymity** cannot be explained and/or maintained:

Anonymity cannot be fully guaranteed in photographs. Though faces will not be included in photographs, identifiers in participants (i.e. clothing, accessories, and etc.) may appear in the photographs.

- 3) Explain why research participants cannot be asked for **approval** for recording and/or particular use of information:

We will ask participants for approval before recording and/or particular use of information. Participants who will be on the farm visit will first recruited via a Qualtrics link on farm tour's Eventbrite website. Those who have not clicked the link and read about the research may now

know about the research until they arrive for the bus trip to the farm. The option for oral consent will be provided in this instance.

4) Explain how you ensure that negative or **harmful impacts** of the research on the research participants will be minimised:

1. We will not invade their privacy when observing. We will enable participants to direct as much of their discussion as possible and not push any person to disclose any more than they appear to want.

C. Researcher Training and Consultation of Professional Guidelines

1) I confirm that in the course of my research design, I have received the following training in the ethical aspects of my research (please give details of any modules, CPD or other research ethics training you have attended in the last 18 months):

Two of us teach research methods and regularly update our teaching materials to cover debates and procedures on ethics in line with professional ethical guideline.

2) I confirm that I have read and carefully considered the ethical guidelines of the main professional associations for my subject area (eg: the ASA ethical guidelines: <https://www.theasa.org/ethics/guidelines.shtml>) and incorporated them into my research design.

Researcher Signature:

Date:

Certificate of Approval

Reference Number	ER/JH974/3
Title Of Project	UKRI transforming food systems- Study six: Farm tour pedagogies
Principal Investigator (PI):	Jesse Hsu
Student	N/A
Collaborators	
Duration Of Approval	1 year 6 months
Expected Start Date	12-Jul-2022
Date Of Approval	12-Jul-2022
Approval Expiry Date	31-Dec-2023
Approved By	Vacancy
Name of Authorised Signatory	Ruth Stirton
Date	12-Jul-2022

*NB. If the actual project start date is delayed beyond 12 months of the expected start date, this Certificate of Approval will lapse and the project will need to be reviewed again to take account of changed circumstances such as legislation, sponsor requirements and University procedures.

Please note and follow the requirements for approved submissions:

Amendments to protocol

- * Any changes or amendments to approved protocols must be submitted to the C-REC for authorisation prior to implementation.

Feedback regarding the status and conduct of approved projects

- * Any incidents with ethical implications that occur during the implementation of the project must be reported immediately to the Chair of the C-REC.

Feedback regarding any adverse(1) and unexpected events(2)

- * Any adverse (undesirable and unintended) and unexpected events that occur during the implementation of the project must be reported to the Chair of the Social Sciences and Arts C-REC. In the event of a serious adverse event, research must be stopped immediately and the Chair alerted within 24 hours of the occurrence.

Monitoring of Approved studies

The University may undertake periodic monitoring of approved studies. Researchers will be requested to report on the outcomes of research activity in relation to approvals that were granted (full applications and amendments).

Research Standards

Failure to conduct University research in alignment with the Code of Practice for Research may be investigated under the Procedure for the Investigation of Allegations of Misconduct in Research or other appropriate internal mechanisms (3). Any queries can be addressed to the Research Governance Office: rgoffice@sussex.ac.uk

(1) An "adverse event" is one that occurs during the course of a research protocol that either causes physical or psychological harm, or increases the risk of physical or psychological harm, or results in a loss of privacy and/or confidentiality to research participant or others.

(2) An "unexpected event" is an occurrence or situation during the course of a research project that was a) harmful to a participant taking part in the research, or b) increased the probability of harm to participants taking part in the research.

(3) <http://www.sussex.ac.uk/staff/research/rqi/policy/research-policy>